

QUALIFICATION SATISFACTION OF COLLEGE STUDENTS
Kolleclerde Təhsil Alan Tələbələrin İxtisas Məmnunluğu

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the quality of student recognition skills in colleges in different regions of Azerbaijan. Research studies; The quality of material and technical education was evaluated in terms of material and technical foundation, social and psychological support services. The research based on quantitative methodology was conducted with the help of 2946 students and the obtained data was analyzed in the SPSS program. The question depends on the environment, teachers, curriculum and labor market availability. In this context, the choice of department is closely related to a number of interests: personal, demand for various professions, family and social influences, as well as the quality of education provided at the university. Greater satisfaction also increases the likelihood of higher academic performance. Research results showed that the majority of students believed that the education they received would have a positive impact on their future career prospects and quality of life. At the same time, ambivalent and negative opinions emphasized the need to increase the practical components of educational programs, expand extracurricular activities and develop social-psychological support services. The results obtained may be useful in developing strategic development plans of universities and strengthening student-centered teaching approaches.

Keywords: college education, specialty satisfaction, motivation, career

ÖZ: Bu çalışma Azerbaycan'ın farklı bölgelerindeki kolejlerde öğrenci tanıma becerisinin kalitesini incelemektedir. Araştırma çalışmaları; materyal ve teknik eğitimin kalitesi, materyal ve teknik temel, sosyal ve psikolojik destek hizmetleri açısından değerlendirildi. Niceliksel metodolojiye dayalı araştırma 2946 öğrencinin yardımıyla yürütülmüş ve elde edilen veriler SPSS programında analiz edilmiştir. Soru çevreye, öğretmenlere, müfredata ve işgücü piyasasının uygunluğuna bağlıdır. Bu bağlamda, bölüm seçimi bir dizi ilgi alanıyla yakından ilişkilidir: kişisel, çeşitli mesleğe olan talep, ailevi ve toplumsal etkiler ve ayrıca üniversitede verilen eğitimin kalitesi. Büyük memnuniyet aynı zamanda daha yüksek akademik performans olasılığını da artırır. Araştırma sonuçları, öğrencilerin çoğunluğunun aldıkları eğitimin gelecekteki kariyer beklentileri ve yaşam kaliteleri üzerinde olumlu etki yaratacağına inandığını göstermiştir. Aynı zamanda kararsız ve olumsuz görüşler, eğitim programlarının pratik bileşenlerinin artırılması, ders dışı etkinliklerin genişletilmesi ve sosyal-psikolojik destek hizmetlerinin geliştirilmesi gerektiğini vurgulamıştır. Elde edilen sonuçlar, üniversitelerin stratejik gelişim planlarının geliştirilmesinde ve öğrenci odaklı öğretim yaklaşımlarının güçlendirilmesinde faydalı olabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: kolej eğitimi, uzmanlık memnuniyeti, motivasyon, kariyer

INTRODUCTION:

Currently, there are a total of 59 colleges operating in the system of secondary vocational education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, of which 53 are state-owned and 6 are private educational institutions. According to the data from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan (SSC) for the year 2023-2024, a total of 65,640 students are enrolled in these educational institutions. Among them, 59,314 students are enrolled in full-time education, while 6,326 are enrolled in part-time education. Of the students, 41,027 are women, and 24,613 are men. These figures regarding the gender composition and forms of education of the students indicate that secondary vocational education institutions occupy an important place in the education system of Azerbaijan. This also highlights the relevance of analyzing the satisfaction level of students regarding the learning environment, quality of teaching, and preparation for the labor market (Qaliboğlu, 2024). Student satisfaction in secondary vocational education institutions is one of the key factors directly influencing their academic success and future career choices (Aydın et al., 2014). In particular, students' satisfaction with their field of study in colleges is crucial in terms of the application of the knowledge and skills they acquire, both in the educational process and in their professional lives. Research shows that when students are satisfied with their chosen field, their academic motivation increases, and their engagement in the educational process strengthens (Zhai, 2012). Moreover, the level of satisfaction broadens students' future career prospects and creates conditions for them to build a more successful professional life. Thus, students who are satisfied with their chosen profession tend to have better conditions for achieving higher success both during their studies and after graduation (Kim, 2018).

In the modern era, the rapidly changing demands of the labor market and the dynamics of a globalizing world turn career choices into a more strategic issue (Euler, 2013). In this context, students' attitudes toward their fields of study in colleges and the compatibility of these fields with the labor market are of significant importance for the development of the education system. Research shows that the alignment of educational institutions with labor demands directly impacts student satisfaction and academic motivation (Pilz, 2016). Field satisfaction is not only an indicator of the quality of educational institutions but also one of the key factors contributing to the social and economic development of society by training more professional specialists (Pilz, 2016). This article aims to investigate the extent to which students in colleges are satisfied with their field of study, how this satisfaction affects their academic performance and future plans. The main goal of the study is to identify students' satisfaction with their field of study, analyze the factors that shape this satisfaction, and propose recommendations for improving the quality of education. This research will contribute to

strengthening a student-centered approach in education policy and management, as well as supporting strategic decision-making. At the same time, the findings will provide useful insights for optimizing teaching methods and improving students' preparedness in line with their career prospects.

Problem

Colleges operating in Azerbaijan's secondary vocational education system play a crucial role in training qualified personnel for various sectors of the country (Qaliboğlu, 2024). However, issues related to students' satisfaction with their chosen field of study remain largely under-researched. The content of educational programs, the lack of practical knowledge, fields of study that do not meet labor market demands, and disparities in the quality of teaching may lead to dissatisfaction among students regarding their chosen profession (Bilgin et al., 2022). Therefore, students' dissatisfaction with their field of study not only weakens their academic motivation but can also lead to lower educational performance, higher dropout rates, and difficulties in making future career choices. The problem of student satisfaction with their education in colleges is one of the key issues faced by both the younger generation and educational institutions. Solving this problem significantly impacts the social status of students within each college and their academic success (Bailey & Xu, 2012). Moreover, low student satisfaction negatively affects the reputation of educational institutions and the development of the country's overall education system. On the other hand, the changing dynamics of the labor market create a mismatch between the required and offered fields of study, resulting in difficulties in job placement for college graduates (Aydemir, 2016). These types of issues make it essential to conduct more extensive research on measuring the satisfaction levels of students in colleges and addressing the existing shortcomings in this area.

Research Objective

The aim of this research is to investigate the level of satisfaction of students studying in colleges with their chosen field of study and the impact of this satisfaction on their education quality, academic outcomes, and future career prospects. The main objective of the study is to identify the key factors (material, social, psychological, and teaching quality-related factors) that influence students' satisfaction.

Research Questions

- What is the overall level of satisfaction of students with their chosen field of study?
- How do teaching quality and infrastructure impact students' satisfaction with their field of study, and to what extent does social and psychological support enhance students' satisfaction with their profession?

- How does field satisfaction influence students' future career prospects and motivations?

Literature Review

Student satisfaction reflects the level of contentment that students derive from their learning environment, teaching quality, and overall educational experiences. To measure college student satisfaction, validated tools include factors such as curriculum, counseling, facilities, and campus climate (Zhai, 2012). Research indicates that student satisfaction is linked not only to academic performance but also to social and emotional factors (Sidorova, 2020). Key factors influencing satisfaction include the infrastructure of the educational institution, teacher support, and the modernity of teaching methods. At the same time, satisfaction is also related to students' expectations regarding their career prospects and how these expectations align with reality (Billett, 2014). Experience-based programs and an education environment focused on practical knowledge shape students' attitudes toward education more positively (Ryazhkin, 2023). Therefore, student satisfaction is not only an indicator of education quality but also a significant factor influencing their motivation and future professional preparation. Students' satisfaction with their chosen field of study creates a strong connection between teaching quality, educational outcomes, and future career prospects. High-quality teaching enhances the effectiveness of the knowledge and skills students gain from their field of study, increasing their academic achievements and strengthening their professional preparation (Billett, 2014). Research shows that a balance between practical components of the curriculum and theoretical knowledge leads students to value their field of study more and better prepares them for the labor market (Sidorova, 2020). Furthermore, students' expectations regarding the labor market prospects of their chosen field shape their satisfaction level and increase their motivation (Carnevale et al., 2012). Thus, field satisfaction directly affects the results students achieve during their education and their future career plans. Therefore, student satisfaction is crucial for academic success, closely linked to improved academic performance, the possibility of continuing education, and decisions regarding additional courses (Sinclair, 2014).

Factors Affecting Career Choice

Various factors influence decision-making processes, including career choices. Professional knowledge and skills, income expectations, status, family and educational environment, and job characteristics play an essential role in career selection (Chen, 2020).

Demographic variables such as gender, marital status, age, employment status, and education level also affect career decisions. Personal interests and competencies are among the most significant factors influencing field choice. When an individual selects a profession that aligns with their interests, they not only enjoy their work but also achieve better results. In this regard, the high quality of colleges, the courses of educational programs, the experience of the teaching staff, and international exposure influence the choices of young people (Danışman et al., 2023). Educational institutions, internship programs, and career preparation activities can guide young people in various directions. Obtaining high-quality education also provides young people with opportunities for international experience and the ability to network with foreign professionals. Students' field choice in colleges is influenced by a variety of social, economic, psychological, and personal factors (Fike et al., 2008). Research shows that several key factors affect students' choices: one of the factors influencing field choice is the state of the job market. The demands of the job market and the need for different professions guide young people's choices (Lee, 2014).

- The family members and close social circle of a young person have a significant influence on their decision-making process. Parents' aspirations, their fields of expertise, and their financial capabilities play a central role in shaping the young person's choices. The impact of family and close social environments on students' field selection is of substantial importance. Moore and Shulock (2009) note that a student's socio-economic background and their parents' attitude toward education significantly guide their career choices.
- Tuition fees, opportunities provided by private educational institutions, the costs associated with studying abroad or attending specialized courses, and other financial factors also influence young people's educational decisions (Chen, 2020). Financial circumstances can lead young people to pursue more lucrative career options and affordable educational programs. Government-funded education programs and scholarships provide some young people with financial means to pursue higher education. Financial difficulties and a lack of resources may steer students toward fields that offer practical, quick employment opportunities. This is particularly true for colleges with budget-friendly education and professional experience opportunities (Moore & Shulock, 2009).
- Teacher support and professionalism enhance students' motivation regarding their chosen field of study. Data indicates that a high-quality

teaching environment influences students' satisfaction with their field of study (Chen, 2020).

- Personal interests and abilities are among the key factors in field selection. Students aim to build a successful career by selecting fields that align with their capabilities (Danışman et al., 2023).
- Practical experience opportunities and the prospects within the job market also play a significant role in the decision-making process. For example, practice-based curricula support students' decisions and enable them to make more reliable career choices (Chen, 2020).
- The social environment and a student's self-assessment also influence field selection. Students with high self-confidence tend to choose more challenging and ambitious fields, while others may opt for more familiar and safer choices (Danışman et al., 2023).
- Another factor influencing field selection is the effect of social networks and the surrounding environment. Young people make their choices based on recommendations from people they know, social networks, and other sources (Fike et al., 2008). The environment, along with the influence of social media, shapes the fields of interest for young people and helps them determine the jobs they wish to pursue.
- Global trends and developments around the world also affect field selection. Factors such as advancements in technology, global economic conditions, wars, and environmental issues can guide young people toward specific fields (Lee, 2014). For example, professions related to environmental issues or modern technologies often capture the attention of young people.
- These factors exert a multifaceted influence on students' field selection and shape the decisions that directly impact their academic and personal lives. Future research should aim to explore the interactions among these factors in greater detail.

The quality of education and infrastructure are among the key determinants of student satisfaction and educational outcomes (Yang, 2021). Educational institutions equipped with the most modern educational infrastructure and utilizing technological tools create more effective learning environments. Electronic resources, online classes, video lessons, and other modern teaching tools provide opportunities tailored to different learning styles (Tessema, 2012). This enhances their education and ultimately increases student achievement. To achieve teaching quality, it is essential that curricula and assessment systems align with modern standards (Ryan et al., 2017). Feedback from teachers helps track progress in the learning process and guides students in the right direction, enhancing their education. This also boosts their motivation and ensures their academic success.

Expanding educational infrastructure helps improve learning and educational outcomes. The combination of physical environments, technological resources, social and sports facilities, and practical learning environments has a significant positive impact on academic success (Sop, 2020). Improving infrastructure ensures greater engagement in new courses, facilitates learning, and ultimately elevates academic performance.

Teaching quality is closely linked to the professionalism of teachers, the relevance of curricula, and the practical application of knowledge. The use of modern technologies and individualized approaches to students are considered key indicators of high-quality teaching and increase students' confidence in the educational process (Pilz, 2016). At the same time, infrastructure, including libraries, laboratories, and technical resources, plays a critical supporting role in students' academic activities (Yang, 2021). Research shows that good infrastructure ensures students have a more comfortable and productive learning environment, positively influencing their overall educational experience (Tessema, 2012). Conversely, a lack of resources and poor infrastructure reduces student satisfaction and negatively affects their academic and career prospects (Sop, 2020). Thus, teaching quality and infrastructure are fundamental elements in shaping student satisfaction with education.

Career Prospects:

Satisfaction with one's field of study reflects the impact of the chosen discipline on students' academic achievements, personal development, and future career prospects. Career development and job satisfaction are linked to an individual's mental health throughout life (Dhaqane et al., 2016). Choosing the right field of study leads to higher motivation in classes and a more serious approach to the learning process. Studies indicate that students who are particularly interested in their field work harder, dedicate more time to classes, and achieve higher academic performance. Horn et al. (2006) noted in their research the significant influence of interest and motivation on academic success.

These developments highlight the importance of aligning career prospects and fields of study with the evolving demands of the global economy and technological landscape. Recent studies emphasize the importance of career prospects and field choices for students' academic success and future opportunities. Personality traits, such as conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness to experience, significantly influence career values and choices among university students (Özok et al., 2022). Rapid technological advancements, especially in artificial intelligence and data science, are reshaping job markets and increasing demand for qualified professionals in fields like accounting. Innovation and startup ecosystems play a crucial role in economic development, with countries competing to

attract and retain innovative startups through venture capital (Dhaqane et al., 2016). Moreover, it has been shown that fostering a diligent work ethic influences career choices, emphasizing the necessity of career-oriented guidance in schools to direct students toward conscious career decisions.

These findings underscore the complex interplay between personal characteristics, educational approaches, and technological trends in shaping career trajectories. Research shows that students demonstrate higher motivation and satisfaction when they believe their field of study has promising prospects in the labor market (Horn et al., 2006). The practical components of educational programs, professional training, and teaching skills aligned with labor market needs form the basis of this satisfaction (Dhaqane et al., 2016). On the other hand, students dissatisfied with their field of study may face difficulties securing a successful position in the labor market, as this dissatisfaction can negatively affect their performance and overall motivation during their education (Özok et al., 2022). Therefore, satisfaction with one's field of study enriches students' educational experiences, shapes their career prospects more clearly, and fosters success in their academic and professional lives.

The social and psychological aspects of student satisfaction significantly influence their academic success and personal development. Student satisfaction is one of the key indicators for measuring the effectiveness and quality of the educational process. This satisfaction is not only related to academic performance but also to social and psychological aspects (Kim et al., 2015). Understanding the social and psychological dimensions of student satisfaction helps educational institutions provide better services to students and support their development.

Students' social well-being is linked to their social interactions within educational institutions. Social interactions are determined by the relationships students have with peers, teachers, and other educational programs (Kuwahara, 2015). Strong and supportive interactions enhance overall social opportunities. For instance, teachers' friendly and understanding approach, mutual trust and cooperation among students, and a friendly classroom atmosphere contribute to students feeling more comfortable during the learning process. Another factor enhancing social opportunities is the social activities organized within the university. Sports, cultural events, student clubs, and volunteer activities can be beneficial for both education and personal development. Such activities provide opportunities to relieve stress, make new friends, and improve social skills (Kuwahara, 2015).

From a psychological perspective, student satisfaction is related to how they feel within the educational environment. This aspect includes the adaptation process to the level of education, teaching methods used by

teachers, assessment techniques, and the style of lessons. Students expect fair and objective systems for evaluating their knowledge and skills. Psychological stability and fairness in the assessment process enhance student success (Özok et al., 2022). Students' psychological well-being is closely related to their sense of confidence. Support and motivation help them discover their potential and achieve better outcomes. Teachers should provide necessary resources and respond to students' psychological concerns to help them succeed. Additionally, stress management programs implemented in educational institutions help students cope with changes and challenges in their study plans. Protecting students from stress and ensuring their well-being enhances the effectiveness of the education system and their psychological capabilities (Kim et al., 2015).

Various social and psychological factors influence the satisfaction of college students. Ethical and moral values play a crucial role in shaping students' experiences, and educational institutions are responsible for passing these values on to future generations. The quality of student-teacher relationships is another important factor that affects both academic and social development. Positive and supportive interactions between students and teachers can bring long-term benefits, while negative interactions can hinder student success (Milsom & Coughlin, 2015). Improving these relationships is essential for creating a better learning environment. The social environment, including students' interactions with teachers, friends, and family, is one of the primary factors shaping their commitment to education and level of satisfaction (OECD, 2020).

Research by Ryazhkin (2023) indicates that sincere relationships and support from teachers make students feel more confident and actively engaged in the educational process. Psychological aspects include students' emotional well-being, stress management skills, and their sense of value within the educational environment. Kuwahara (2015) highlights that a strong social support system and a healthy psychological environment among students increase their motivation and help them handle challenges in the educational process more effectively. Conversely, social isolation and a lack of emotional support can lead to decreased motivation and a negative attitude toward the educational process (Kim et al., 2015). Thus, the social and psychological aspects of student satisfaction play a crucial role in ensuring the success of their overall educational experience.

The **Community Colleges** and **Vocational Schools** systems in the United States offer various advantages for student satisfaction and career prospects. These institutions provide affordable tuition, flexible schedules, and programs tailored to local labor market demands, enabling students to make convenient and goal-oriented choices (Horn & Nevill, 2006). The impact of student satisfaction on field selection is primarily related to the practical

orientation of educational programs and their alignment with future career opportunities (Kim et al., 2015).

In terms of teaching quality and infrastructure, while these institutions are equipped with highly qualified instructors and modern training laboratories, disparities in material and technical resources in certain regions create challenges (Bailey & Xu, 2012). Regarding career prospects, vocational school graduates gain direct access to the job market, which significantly enhances their satisfaction (Carnevale et al., 2012). On the other hand, Community College graduates can continue their education in bachelor's programs, which offer higher earning potential (Moore & Shulock, 2009).

From social and psychological perspectives, these institutions create inclusive educational environments by serving diverse student groups. However, addressing the socio-economic and academic support needs of these students significantly influences overall satisfaction levels (Fike & Fike, 2008). In general, while Community Colleges and Vocational Schools play a crucial role in meeting student needs and preparing them for career paths, ensuring equal resource distribution and strengthening support mechanisms is vital for achieving sustainable positive outcomes.

Secondary Vocational Education in Western Europe:

In Western Europe, secondary vocational education focuses on balancing practical and theoretical knowledge to enhance student satisfaction. Germany's **Dual Education System** and France's **Brevet de Technicien Supérieur (BTS)** programs are considered some of the most successful models in this field. Student satisfaction is mainly linked to the alignment of educational programs with labor market demands and the opportunity to gain experience in real work environments (Pilz, 2016).

Factors influencing field selection include parental recommendations, labor market demands, and the opportunities offered by educational institutions (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Advanced laboratories and the use of modern technologies in education contribute to higher student performance (OECD, 2020).

Regarding career prospects, these systems prepare students for direct entry into the job market and are associated with high employment rates. For instance, most graduates of Germany's Dual Education System find jobs in their fields of study (Euler, 2013).

In terms of social and psychological aspects, research by Billett (2014) shows that the presence of mentoring and support mechanisms in educational institutions enhances students' academic and emotional well-being. Overall, secondary vocational education in Western Europe provides a model that ensures student satisfaction and career prospects through labor market-aligned curricula and practical skills.

Secondary Vocational Education in East Asia:

In East Asia, particularly in countries like Japan, South Korea, and China, secondary vocational education is structured to meet economic demands and technological advancements. Student satisfaction is primarily related to the labor market-oriented programs and the development of practical skills offered by these institutions. For example, Japan's **Kosen Technical Colleges** provide students with advanced technical knowledge and practical experience, enhancing their satisfaction levels (Kuwahara, 2015).

Lee et al. (2014) suggest that factors influencing field selection in South Korea include family influence, industry demands, and government education policies. Kim (2018) correlates the choice of technical education with stable job opportunities and income prospects in the job market.

Regarding teaching quality and infrastructure, technical schools and colleges in these countries are equipped with modern technologies and innovative teaching methods. The Chinese government has made significant investments in modernizing the infrastructure of vocational education institutions, positively impacting teaching quality.

Career prospects for graduates are excellent, with high employment rates. For instance, over 90% of vocational school graduates in China find jobs in their fields of study (Chen et al., 2020).

In terms of social and psychological aspects, mentoring and support programs in these countries improve students' academic success and emotional well-being. Research by Lee et al. (2014) indicates that mentoring support in South Korea helps students develop personally and make better field choices.

Overall, secondary vocational education in East Asia offers a balanced approach to ensuring students' career development and social and psychological well-being.

Methodology:

This study employs a quantitative approach to investigate the satisfaction levels of students in colleges regarding their chosen fields. A quantitative methodology provides an objective framework for evaluating the current state of student satisfaction and obtaining specific indicators in this area.

Research Design

The study is based on a descriptive quantitative research model. This model aims to describe students' satisfaction levels regarding their field selection and identify differences based on various demographic factors.

Data Collection

A survey method was used to collect data. The survey was designed to measure the satisfaction of college students with their fields of study, the factors affecting this satisfaction, and their perspectives on education and career prospects. The survey form consists of two main sections:

1. **Demographic Data:** Age, gender, field of study, and other socio-demographic characteristics of students.
2. **Satisfaction Measures:** Questions exploring students' views on the quality of educational programs, learning environments, teacher professionalism, availability of teaching resources, and alignment with labor market demands.

Sampling

The study targeted students enrolled in various colleges across different regions of Azerbaijan. A random sampling method was employed, and 2,946 students from five colleges (Agdam State Social-Economic College, Agdash State Humanitarian College, Agdam State Socio-Economic College, Tovuz State Socio-Economic College, Ganja State Regional College and Shirvan State Economics and Humanitarian College participated in the survey. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software.

Reliability and Validity:

To ensure the validity of the survey questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted with 50 students. Necessary adjustments were made to the survey questions based on the pilot study results. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha method, and an average score of 0.91 was achieved, meeting relevant scientific standards.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha value

Q1	0,88	Q8	0,95	Q15	0,42
Q2	0,70	Q9	0,86	Q16	0,40
Q3	1,57	Q10	1,27	Q17	0,78
Q4	0,61	Q11	1,39	Q18	1,19
Q5	0,41	Q12	0,56	Q19	1,47
Q6	0,59	Q13	0,69	Cronbach's Alpha total value: 0.905	
Q7	0,78	Q14	0,32		

This methodological approach provides an opportunity to collect detailed and objective information about students' satisfaction with their specialty and to analyze existing problems in this area in depth.

Limitations:

- **Geographical limitation of the research:** Since the study is limited to colleges located in the regions, the results do not cover all secondary specialized educational institutions in the country. This restricts the generalization of the research results on a national scale.
- **Selection of respondents:** The students participating in the research are only individuals studying in 6 randomly selected colleges. This selection may not fully reflect the opinions and experiences of all regional college students.
- **Data collection methods and tools:** The quantitative method used in the research may yield different results compared to other research methods. For instance, using more in-depth qualitative methods could allow a broader exploration of the reasons for student satisfaction.
- **Subjective responses:** Data obtained through the survey reflects the subjective opinions of students. In some cases, this may not fully represent the real situation and could affect the accuracy of the results.
- **Time limitation:** The research was conducted within a specific time frame (November 1-30, 2024), so dynamic changes affecting students' satisfaction with their specialty may not have been considered.

Findings and Discussion:

A total of 2,946 people participated in the survey. Of these, 884 people, or 30%, were men, and 2,062 people, or 70%, were women.

Graph 1: The graph of students' admission scores to college based on gender dependency.

As seen from the graph, the majority of students were admitted to colleges by scoring within the 81-120 points range. When viewed as percentages rather than quantities for each category, it is observed that among those who scored below 80 points, 9% were women, and 14% were men. Among those who scored within the 81-120 points range, 68% were women, and 66% were men. In the 121-160 points range, 19% of the scorers were women, and 17% were men. In the 161-200 points range, the percentage of both men and women was 1%. Lastly, the percentage of respondents scoring 200 points and above was 0.5% for both men and women. These results indicate that college admission scores are not dependent on gender.

Graph 2. Gender Dependency in Students' Specializations

The data indicates significant differences in the number of male and female students across various fields of study. These differences suggest that certain specializations are influenced by gender-related perceptions and interests. Women dominate the fields of social services and education, accounting for 88% and 81%, respectively. This supports the idea that social and educational service fields are traditionally associated with women. Special measures are needed to increase men's interest in these areas.

In finance-related fields, women also have a significant presence, making up 74% of students. This could indicate a stronger interest among women in finance and economics. In the ICT field, the gender distribution among students is relatively balanced, although men are slightly underrepresented at 42%. This points to a growing interest in technology among women. To maintain gender balance, equal incentive mechanisms can be implemented for both genders.

In the agricultural sector, the number of male and female students is nearly equal, suggesting that this field is equally appealing and suitable for both genders. Conversely, men traditionally dominate the technical service field, representing 55% of students.

The prevalence of female students in social services, finance, and education fields reflects the influence of gender-related stereotypes on these areas. Meanwhile, a relatively balanced gender distribution is observed in agriculture, ICT, and technical specializations. Measures supporting gender equality should be continued to maintain this balance.

Graph 3. Factors Influencing Specialization Choices

These reasons are both similar and different in certain nuances when analyzed from a gender perspective. It was noted that 0.4% of women and 3% of men chose this field for personal reasons. The desire to enter university as a sub-bachelor is almost the same, with 41% of men and 42% of women sharing this intention. Among those admitted to college because their favorite field of study is available there, 16% are women, and 21% are men. Among those who chose college because their exam scores were insufficient for university admission, 26% are men, and 32% are women. Due to family expectations, social circumstances, and financial challenges, 3% of men and 10% of women opted for college. Another differentiating factor relates to male students: 0.4% (35 individuals) of the male students surveyed stated that they chose college just to "have a diploma."

Student Satisfaction

The questions presented to students can be categorized into the following subgroups:

1. Satisfaction with Future Career Prospects
2. Satisfaction with the Quality of Education and Teachers
3. Satisfaction with Infrastructure
4. Self-Confidence

Future Career Prospects

Questions in this subgroup reflect students' expectations regarding their future careers, the impact of career choices on their quality of life, the relevance of their field of study to the labor market, and their overall educational aspirations.

General Analysis

The majority of students expressed positive views about the impact of their career choices on their quality of life (78%), the relevance of their field of study to the labor market (77%), and their ability to find work in their area of study (69%). The relatively high percentage of overall optimism regarding education and career (78%) compared to other indicators demonstrates students' belief in the broad opportunities that education can provide.

Alignment

The majority of respondents believe that their chosen field of study will positively impact their future lives and be beneficial in the labor market. This reflects a general consensus that the fields of study align with market demands. The close correlation between positive responses regarding educational and career aspirations and the impact of career choices on quality of life underscores the connection between these two aspects.

Differences

Students' overall optimism about education (78%) is higher than their confidence in finding a job in their field of study (69%). This difference indicates that students have greater faith in the broader developmental prospects' education provides than in specific job opportunities. Similarly, the positive views about the relevance of their field of study to the labor market (77%) exceed confidence in finding a job, suggesting that students are more assured of their education's alignment with market needs than of securing employment.

Uncertainty and Negative Feedback

There are notable variations in the rates of uncertainty (14%–26%) and negative responses (4%–5%) across all questions. The highest level of uncertainty is related to finding a suitable job in the labor market (26%), reflecting students' concerns about labor market unpredictability. On the other hand, negative responses regarding educational and career aspirations (4%) are the lowest, indicating an overall sense of optimism.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The majority of students believe that their education will positively impact their future lives and careers. However, uncertainties and negative responses indicate concerns about finding suitable jobs in the labor market. These results highlight the need for educational programs to be more market-oriented, with increased practical experience and enhanced career-focused guidance. Collaborating with employers and implementing initiatives to inform students about their future prospects will further enhance student satisfaction.

Teaching Quality and Satisfaction with Teachers

In this subgroup, the survey results reflect students' views on the quality of teaching, extracurricular activities, support from teachers, and teaching methods. The analysis evaluates students' overall satisfaction levels, uncertainties, and issues related to these areas.

Overall Analysis

The general satisfaction level regarding teaching quality is high, with the majority of respondents (82%) satisfied with the quality of teaching at their colleges. This indicates that educational institutions are meeting students' academic needs. High satisfaction with teachers' professionalism (85%) and teaching methods (81%) supports this result. However, satisfaction with extracurricular activities and training programs is lower (51%), suggesting that colleges need further development in these areas.

Alignments

Respondents are generally satisfied with teaching quality, teachers' professionalism, and teaching methods. Positive feedback regarding teachers' support (80%) indicates strong teacher-student relationships. These alignments emphasize colleges' ability to organize the teaching process effectively and meet students' academic needs.

Differences

Satisfaction with extracurricular activities and training programs (51%) is significantly lower than with other indicators. This difference suggests that the additional activities and development opportunities in colleges do not meet students' expectations. Additionally, uncertainty about teaching quality (13%) is much lower than uncertainty about extracurricular activities (27%), highlighting a lack of information about additional activities.

Uncertainty and Negative Feedback

Uncertainty is most prevalent regarding extracurricular activities (26.94%) and training programs, indicating that students may not be sufficiently informed about these opportunities. Negative feedback is generally low (5%–10%), but higher for extracurricular activities (22%), suggesting there is a need for more support in developing social and practical skills.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Overall satisfaction with teaching quality and teachers' activities is high. However, there is a need to enhance extracurricular activities and enrich teaching quality with personalized approaches and practical training. To eliminate uncertainty and negative feedback, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Expansion of Extracurricular Activities:** Additional activities and training programs should be organized to develop students' social and practical skills.
2. **Improvement of Teaching Quality:** The application of modern methodologies and an increase in resources will further enhance teaching quality.
3. **Strengthening Teacher-Student Relationships:** Continuous training should be organized to improve teachers' ability to approach students individually.

This analysis shows that the overall teaching quality at colleges is satisfactory, but improvements in extracurricular opportunities and teacher-student relations will further enhance the students' educational experience.

Infrastructure

This subgroup reflects students' opinions on the existing material-technical base, social and public environment, the organization of class schedules, and rules for promoting a healthy lifestyle. Survey results identify the general satisfaction level of students with their colleges' infrastructure, existing deficiencies, and areas with potential for improvement.

Overall Analysis

The majority of students are satisfied with their colleges' material-technical base (64%), the organization of class schedules (77%), and rules for promoting a healthy lifestyle (74%). The convenient location of the colleges is also positively evaluated (72%). However, satisfaction with the social and psychological environment is slightly lower (68%), indicating a need for improvement in this area.

Alignments

Respondents have expressed high levels of satisfaction with the material-technical base, class schedules, and rules for promoting a healthy lifestyle. This indicates that colleges provide the necessary resources for teaching and daily activities and are generally successful in meeting students' needs.

Differences

Satisfaction with the social and psychological environment (68%) is slightly lower compared to satisfaction with the rules for promoting a healthy lifestyle (74%). This difference may suggest that social support mechanisms are not as effective for some students. Additionally, the rate of uncertainty is higher regarding the material-technical base (23%) and the social environment (19%), highlighting a lack of information and support in these areas.

Uncertainty and Negative Feedback

The higher uncertainty, particularly regarding the material-technical base (23%) and the rules for a healthy lifestyle (15%), suggests insufficient information on these topics. Negative feedback is generally low (9%-13%), but negative feedback related to the social environment and rules for a healthy lifestyle is more notable. This implies the need for a more inclusive and functional infrastructure for students in these areas.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Although the infrastructure at colleges is considered satisfactory by the majority of students, there is room for improvement in certain areas. This includes further enhancing the social-psychological environment, the healthy lifestyle programs, and the material-technical base. The following recommendations are made to improve satisfaction in these areas:

1. **Enhancement of Material-Technical Base:** Expanding the material-technical resources to increase opportunities for practical experience and the use of modern resources (Zborovski, 2021).
2. **Strengthening Social and Psychological Support:** Organizing psychological counseling services and social events will improve students' overall well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2017).
3. **Increasing Opportunities for Healthy Lifestyle:** The establishment of sports facilities, health centers, and healthy eating initiatives will contribute to students' well-being (OECD, 2020).

This analysis shows that while colleges meet students' infrastructure needs, further development of the social environment and material-technical resources will enhance students' overall satisfaction.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The results of this subgroup indicate that the majority of students believe their education has a positive impact on their self-confidence and professional development opportunities. However, for some students, more support and clarity are needed. The following recommendations could help enhance satisfaction levels:

1. **Emphasizing Practical Aspects of Education:** The slightly lower confidence in professional development opportunities (67%) compared to the increase in self-confidence (74%) suggests a need for further focus on the practical application of education. Implementing more hands-on learning experiences and career-oriented workshops would better prepare students for their future careers.
2. **Balancing Academic and Social Life:** The satisfaction with student life (70%) is slightly lower than the satisfaction with family and social support (87%). Colleges could consider providing more opportunities for students to engage in extracurricular activities, fostering a balance between academic and social life, which could further improve their overall satisfaction.
3. **Strengthening Career Support:** To address the uncertainty about career prospects (27% uncertainty regarding professional development), colleges should offer more career counseling services, internships, and networking opportunities with professionals in students' fields. This would help students gain a clearer understanding of how their education aligns with career opportunities.
4. **Enhancing Social Support Services:** Although family and social support received high ratings (87%), ensuring that all students have access to strong social support networks within the campus, such as mentorship programs and peer support groups, can further enhance their personal growth and sense of belonging.

By addressing these areas, colleges can strengthen their support for students, improving both their academic experience and overall satisfaction.

1. Strengthening Practical Education: It is essential to enhance the practical aspects of education programs and provide clearer information about students' career prospects (Bilgin et al., 2022). This could involve incorporating more hands-on experiences, internships, and real-world applications within the curriculum to better prepare students for the workforce.

2. Social Support and Motivation: Strengthening connections with family and social environments and organizing special events to increase students' motivation is crucial (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Providing more opportunities for students to engage with their families, peers, and mentors would help improve their overall motivation and sense of belonging.

3. Improving Student Life: To reduce negative feedback about student life, social, academic, and emotional support services should be expanded (Zborovski, 2021). Creating a supportive and inclusive campus environment where students can receive assistance in balancing academic pressures with social and emotional challenges will contribute to their overall well-being.

This analysis indicates that colleges are generally successful in supporting students' self-confidence and professional development. However, strengthening practical training and career support could further improve students' educational experiences.

Students' Recommendations: The majority of students (75%) would recommend their college or field of study to others. This demonstrates that the quality of education, infrastructure, and the overall academic environment in colleges is meeting the expectations of most students. The high recommendation rate signals that education positively impacts their academic and personal growth. However, there are still some students who remain undecided (15%) or have negative views (10%), indicating uncertainty or dissatisfaction with aspects like education quality, career prospects, or personal experiences. This group requires more attention, as their concerns can highlight areas for improvement in colleges.

Students' Feedback on Desired Changes: When asked about what changes they would like to see in their college experience, students provided interesting responses. These responses could guide further improvements in the college environment to meet students' evolving needs.

Chart 4: StudentRequests

Administrative and Pedagogical Staff:

In this area, students requesting changes have expressed that 10% would like to be taught by younger and more professional teachers, while 38% want the students’ preferences to be considered when selecting group leaders and teachers. Additionally, 52% of students believe that there is a need to change the current college leadership.

Infrastructure:

The majority of students requesting changes in this area have highlighted the need for improvements such as electronic boards (13%), various laboratories (17%), fast internet (36%), and the installation of cameras in rooms and corridors (8%). Furthermore, 14% of students stated that the heating system and 10% mentioned the college's canteen do not meet their needs, and both areas need improvement.

Extracurricular Activities:

Students who want changes in extracurricular activities have emphasized the need for various competitions, events, festivals, and excursions. Organizing competitions and contests could help develop students’ competitiveness, teamwork, and leadership skills. These activities would also be effective in increasing students’ motivation and academic interest. Events and festivals are essential for strengthening social connections, creating a collective spirit, and enhancing students' well-being outside of the academic environment. Excursions provide excellent opportunities for students to gain new knowledge and experiences, and extracurricular activities can broaden their interests while helping them apply knowledge in practical settings.

Teaching:

Students requesting changes in teaching methods mainly focus on optimizing lessons, replacing subjects unrelated to their specialties, and prioritizing active learning methods. The teaching of subjects unrelated to students' majors and the organizational shortcomings of lessons can negatively affect their educational experience. Furthermore, the suggestions regarding the

application of active teaching methods align with modern educational standards. In relation to this area, 20% of students have also requested more transparency in exams. The demand for greater exam transparency could stem from several reasons:

The concerns raised by students regarding the examination system and other aspects of their academic experience highlight several key areas for improvement:

1. **Examination Transparency:**

- **Lack of Clear Evaluation Criteria:** Students have expressed concerns that the grading criteria are not fully clear, which may lead to confusion and frustration.
- **Inadequate Transparency in the Examination Process:** There is a lack of transparency in the exam process, and students feel that they are not provided with enough information about how the exams are graded or assessed.
- **Doubts About Teacher Objectivity:** Students have doubts about the approach and objectivity of their teachers when grading exams, which could undermine their confidence in the fairness of the system.

2. **Student Satisfaction:**

- **Flexible Study Programs for Married Students:** Married students have expressed a desire for more flexible study programs and certain concessions to better balance their family responsibilities with academic commitments.
- **Inclusive Approaches for Disabled Students:** Students with disabilities expect more inclusive approaches and support within educational institutions, ensuring they have equal opportunities to succeed.
- **Increase in Scholarships:** 25% of students have called for an increase in scholarships, as this would improve their academic life quality and financial well-being.
- **Longer Breaks Between Classes:** 30% of students have requested longer breaks between classes, highlighting the need for more rest and recovery time.
- **Consideration of Medical Documentation During Illness:** 20% of students reported that the medical documents they submit during illness are not properly considered, and absences are not excused, which negatively affects their academic progress.
- **Improvement of Hygiene and Sanitation:** 25% of students emphasized the importance of improved hygiene and sanitation, particularly the cleanliness of toilets, sanitary facilities, and

general campus cleanliness, which directly impact their health and well-being.

These concerns reflect practical challenges that students face in their academic life. Addressing these issues is essential for improving their overall experience and satisfaction. Educational institutions should prioritize understanding these needs and develop solutions to enhance students' academic success, social well-being, and general satisfaction.

General Results and Recommendations

The survey results indicate that students generally have positive opinions regarding the quality of teaching, material-technical infrastructure, and social environment at colleges. However, indecisive and negative feedback suggests that there are areas with potential for development. Therefore, the following recommendations are proposed to address these areas:

1. Improvement of Teaching Quality:

- **Implementation of Modern Teaching Methodologies:** The introduction of active learning methods and the expansion of practical teaching techniques are crucial for engaging students and enhancing learning outcomes.
- **Optimization of Non-Specialized Courses:** The curriculum should be revised to reduce unnecessary courses and include more elective modules that align with students' interests and career aspirations.
- **Increase in Practical Training:** More practical training sessions should be integrated into the curriculum, and students should be provided with real work experience to better prepare them for their future careers.

2. Infrastructure Enhancement:

- **Provision of Modern Technological Resources:** Electronic boards, diverse laboratories, and high-speed internet should be made available to create a more conducive learning environment.
- **Improvement of Heating and Sanitation Systems:** The current heating and sanitation systems should be upgraded to ensure students' comfort and well-being.
- **Renovation of Social Facilities:** Updating social amenities such as cafeterias, student clubs, and sports facilities is necessary to improve the overall campus experience.

3. Expansion of Extracurricular Activities:

- **Organizing Competitions, Excursions, and Events:** Colleges should host competitions, excursions, and various social events to foster students' teamwork, leadership skills, and engagement.
- **Strengthening Social Interactions:** Organizing celebrations and social gatherings will help build stronger connections among students, enhancing the campus community.

- **Development of Interest-based Programs:** Extracurricular training programs related to students' interests should be created to enrich their learning experience beyond academics.
4. **Strengthening Psychological and Social Support Services:**
 - **Creation of Counseling Centers:** Psychological counseling services should be available to support students' emotional well-being.
 - **Individualized Consultation Services:** Support services addressing the influences of family and social environments should be made available to students.
 - **Special Programs for Economically and Socially Disadvantaged Students:** Programs that cater specifically to students facing financial and social challenges should be developed.
 5. **More Attention to Student Feedback:**
 - **Regular Surveys:** Colleges should conduct regular surveys to gather student feedback on various aspects of college life.
 - **Involvement of Students in Decision-Making:** Students' opinions should be taken into account when selecting group leaders and teachers, promoting a more inclusive decision-making process.
 - **Effective Communication Mechanisms:** Creating efficient communication channels between administration and students will ensure that students' needs and concerns are better addressed.
 6. **Transparency in Examination Processes:**
 - **Clear Grading Criteria:** Grading criteria should be disclosed beforehand to ensure that students are well-informed about how their work will be assessed.
 - **Establishment of Dispute Resolution Mechanisms:** A clear and effective process for students to contest examination results should be introduced.
 - **Use of Technology for Objective Assessment:** Incorporating technology to enhance fairness and objectivity in the evaluation process is necessary.
 7. **Creating Conditions for Married and Disabled Students:**
 - **Flexible Study Options for Married Students:** The education system should offer more flexibility for married students to accommodate their family responsibilities.
 - **Infrastructure Improvements for Disabled Students:** The college infrastructure should be made more accessible, and tailored support programs should be created for students with disabilities.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that while students are generally satisfied with the quality of education, material-technical infrastructure, and social environment at colleges, there are still significant areas for improvement. In

particular, aligning education programs more closely with the labor market, expanding extracurricular activities, and enhancing social and psychological support services will greatly improve students' overall educational experience and future prospects. The results of this study will serve as a valuable roadmap for the development of strategies to better meet student needs and improve the overall educational environment in colleges.

References

- Aydemir, E. (2016). Öğrenci Memnuniyeti açısından üniversiteler arası sıralamada yeni bir sistem önerisi. *Yüksek öğretim Dergisi*, 6(3), 128–141. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2399/yod.16.011>
- Aydın, S., Görmüş, A. Ş., & Altıntop, M. Y. (2014). Öğrencilerin memnuniyet düzeyleri ile demografik özellikleri arasındaki ilişkinin doğrusal olmayan kanonik korelasyon analizi ile incelenmesi: Meslek yüksekokulunda bir uygulama. *AİBÜ Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 14(1), 14–35. <https://doi.org/10.11616/AbantSbe.475>
- Azərbaycan Respublikasının Dövlət Statistika Komitəsi, (ARDSK, 2024). Orta ixtisas təhsili müəssisələri <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/education/#>
- Bailey, T., & Xu, D. (2012). Input-adjusted graduation rates and college accountability: What is known from twenty years of research? *Journal of Higher Education*, 83(4), 485-502. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jhe.2012.0029>
- Billett, S. (2014). The standing of vocational education: Sources of its societal esteem and implications for its enactment. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 66(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2014.894638>
- Bilgin, A., Özdemir, L., Şahan, F. U., Dönmez, A. A., & Kapucu, S. (2022). Öğrencilerin öğrenme çıktılarından memnuniyeti anketinin Türkçe geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Hemşirelik Fakültesi Dergisi*. <https://doi.org/10.31125/hunhemsire.1167269>
- Carnevale, A. P., Smith, N., & Strohl, J. (2012). *Recovery: Job growth and education requirements through 2020*. Georgetown University Center on Education and the Workforce.
- Chen, X., Liu, H., & Zha, Q. (2020). Employment outcomes of vocational education graduates in China: A case study. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 77, 102-137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2020.102237>
- Danışman, B., Sarul, G., Amini, N., Ada, O. O., Aktaş, S. G., Kılıç, S. İ. (2023). METU students' college life satisfaction. *Middle East Technical University Department of Statistics*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.15320>
- Dhaqane, M. K., & Afrah, N. A. (2016). Satisfaction of students and academic performance. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(24), 59-63. <https://doi.org/10.21325/jotags.2020.591>
- Euler, D. (2013). *Germany's dual vocational training system: A model for other countries?* Bertelsmann Stiftung
- Fike, D. S., & Fike, R. (2008). Predictors of first-year student retention in the community college. *Community College Review*, 36(2), 68-88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091552108320222>
- Horn, L., & Nevill, S. (2006). *Profile of undergraduates in U.S. postsecondary education institutions: 2003–04*. National Center for Education Statistics

- Kim, J. (2018). The role of vocational education in South Korea's economic development: Past success and future challenges. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 7(3), 292-305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-10-2017-0095>
- Kim, J., Tamborini, C. R., & Sakamoto, A. (2015). Field of study in college and lifetime earnings in the United States. *Sociology of Education*, 88(4), 320-339. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038040715602132>
- Kuwahara, T. (2015). Japanese Kosen model: A successful example of STEM education at the college level. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 177, 360-364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.02.355>
- Qaliboğlu E. (2024). Ali məktəbdə müəllim-tələbə münasibətlərinin elmi-pedaqoji əsasları. *Azərbaycan məktəbi*. 2(707), səh. 90-96. DOI: 10.30546/32898065.2024.2.090
- Lee, M., Lee, H., & Lee, J. (2014). Factors influencing career decision-making of vocational school students in South Korea. *International Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 22(2), 35-50.
- Milsom, A., Coughlin, J. (2015). Satisfaction With College Major: A Grounded Theory Study, *NACADA Journal*. 35(2), 5-14. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12930/NACADA-14-026>
- Moore, C., & Shulock, N. (2009). *Student progress toward degree completion: Lessons from the research literature*. Institute for Higher Education Leadership & Policy
- OECD. (2020). *VET in a time of crisis: Building foundations for resilient and sustainable skills systems*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/cf6a92a5-en>
- Özok, H., İ., Kayri, M., Tanhan, F. (2022). Üniversite öğrencilerinde memnuniyet ölçüğü: Geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Van Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 19(2), 446-461. <https://doi.org/10.33711/yyuefd.1108292>
- Pilz, M. (2016). Vocational education and training in Germany: Modernisation and new challenges. *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft*, 19(S2), 281-301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11618-016-0724-0>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness*. Guilford Publications
- Ryazhkin A.O. (2023). Удовлетворенность учебной деятельностью и совладающее поведение студентов вуза. *Психологические исследования*. 16(87). 1-19
- Sidorova E.V. (2020). Удовлетворенность студентов-очников бакалавриата СФУ учебным процессом. Nəşr edilməmiş dissertasiya işi.
- Sinclair, Jollean K. (2014). An Empirical Investigation of Student Satisfaction with College Courses. *Research in Higher Education Journal*. 22, 53-69
- Sop, S. A. (2020). Eğitim-Öğretim Memnuniyeti, Akademik Erteleme Eğilimi ve Akademik Başarı İlişkisi, *Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies*, 8 (2), 983-996, <https://doi.org/10.21325/jotags.2020.591>
- Tessema, M., Ready, K., & Yu, W. (2012). Factors affecting college students' satisfaction with major curriculum: Evidence from nine years of data. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(2), 34-44.
- Yang, J., Seo, J. (2021). Effects of College Life Satisfaction, Major Satisfaction and Academic Self-efficacy on School Loyalty, *Journal of Advanced Researches and*

- Reports Vol.1, No.3 (2021), pp.31-38.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.21742/jarr.2021.1.3.05>
- Zborovski Q.E. (2021) Удовлетворенность студентов колледжей и вузов образованием. *Образование: вызовы нового времени*. 27(4). 177-192
- Zhai, Lijuan. (2012). Validation of an Instrument to Measure Community College Student Satisfaction. *Community College Journal of Research and Practice*. 36. 47 - 58.